

FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S TOLERANCE OF AGE FROM 5 TO 7

Shynkareva Zh.

*Ph.D. student**Izmail State University of Humanities*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7828140>**Abstract**

The urgency of the covered issue is due to the peculiarities of the modern development of our country. Year after year, Ukraine becomes more open to the whole world, what requires the readiness of Ukrainian society to understand, perceive and respect the diversity of cultures, views and forms of expression and manifestations of human individuality. Ukrainian society today is witnessing an epoch-making event that opens the door to casual communication, cooperation and interaction of different nations and cultures. Therefore, the problem of tolerance covers all spheres of public life, such as social, religious, political, personal and inter-ethnic.

At the same time, the problem of society's tolerance is closely linked to the process of globalization, which deals with the national and ethnic identities of different cultures and people. The analysis of scientific achievements, which highlights certain aspects of the humanization of the educational process in educational institutions, shows the positive dynamics of the following trends, as a rule, modern parents mostly care about the child's material security, providing the best educational services. In addition, the entertainment industry for children has been developing rapidly. Parents consider their responsibility to entertain, feed, and educate their children. Thus, according to the pedagogical practice, children aim to get most of their pleasure and entertainment in life. The rhythm of modern life causes the spread of a situation where parents spend a lot of time talking on mobile phones, computers, so they lose time for personal communication with children and open conversations. As a result, the educational influence of the family as a social institution is impoverished, which has a decisive influence on the formation of tolerance as a moral quality of the child at the stage of his preschool childhood.

Based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature and self-reflection of own experience of humanization of education of preschool and primary school children, contradictions were revealed between society's demand for a tolerant personality and insufficient focus of preschool and primary education on its formation; between the importance of the effective practical nature of the pedagogical influence on the process of educating tolerance in childhood and the underestimation of resources before school and the initial stages of becoming a child as a student.

The desire to find ways to resolve the contradictions between society's demand for a tolerant personality and the lack of focus of the educational process of preschool and primary education on its formation; between the importance of the effective, practical nature of the pedagogical influence on the process of educating tolerance in childhood and the underestimation of resources before school and the initial stages of the child's development as a student highlighted the relevance of the issue.

Keywords: tolerance, children, pedagogical conditions, kindergarten, social competence, multicultural society.

Introduction. World achievements, modern discoveries, scientific and technological progress are rapidly changing the world around us, the economy, the culture of the planet. There are times in the distant past of the original existence of individual states. Our time is characterized by high mobility of the population, ability of movement, the creation of international, multicultural programs, production and more. One corporation contains an unlimited number of employees from around the world, who differ not only in skin color and traditions, but also in the key values, priorities, rules of conduct. In the conditions of multicultural cooperation, tolerance should become the unifying link, the way to the peaceful existence of the world community, the only principle of human life. Tolerance should be the foundation for building peaceful relations, settling interpersonal and intergroup relations, forming basic human values, so called mutual respect, humanity, acceptance, democracy, and human rights.

Travelling around the world, it should be paid attention to cultural monuments and architectural features of the state and noted the monotony of means of

transportation (airplanes, trains, taxis), places of common residence (airports, canteens, fast food, hotels). External similarity, however, does not address the issue of interpersonal, intergroup and inter-ethnic relations. Every year the population grows, urbanization and wages gather under one roof a huge number of people. Capitals are overcrowded, the world is getting closer, trying to regulate the rules of public life. But religions, cultures, traditions of different countries are often the basis of misunderstandings, quarrels, armed conflicts and so on. We do not know exactly which path the development of mankind will take.

It can be assumed that in the next century, the urbanization and globalization of the world will lead to the destruction of the identity and historical values of the person of the world. Only tolerance, as tolerance for another, can save the identity of each nation, create new human traditions and adopt a universal code of peaceful existence.

It should be noted that the interest in the topic of tolerance has been growing in Ukraine. The instability

of the state's borders, the presence of hostilities and discrimination against the rights and territorial integrity of Ukraine have attracted the attention of the world community to our state. The people of the country have never valued their traditions, roots, norms and values, cultural heritage and history of the state before the independence of Ukraine. The holiday of embroidery, towels, Cossack day, even viburnum on the shoulder straps of the military armed forces are the signs of modernity which unites us with our roots, give us strength and inspiration, teach us to value our native land. The very acceptance of man into his circle is the basis of national unity. However, misunderstandings and fights break out between the denominations "own" and "foreign". Those who are not like us (not with us) are against us. Recently, the world community is watching with interest the changes in the life of our country. Year after year, Ukraine becomes more open to the whole world, which in turn requires the readiness of Ukrainian society to understand, perceive and respect the diversity of cultures, views and forms of expression and manifestations of human individuality. Ukrainian society today is witnessing an epoch-making event that opens the door to casual communication, cooperation and interaction of different nations and cultures. Therefore, the problem of tolerance covers all spheres of public life, such as social, religious, political, personal and inter-ethnic.

The subconscious feeling of antipathy (sympathy), which is the basis of the principle of complementarity, determined the division of social groups and individuals into their own and others, as a guarantee of biological survival and natural competition. According to its geographical location, Ukraine unites the inhabitants of almost all religious denominations of the world, different cultures, national communities. It is known that the roots of the conflict are not in external human behavior, the war begins with the violation of internal borders. That's why the main factor in the peaceful existence of the country and the stability of its borders are ethical issues, education, diversity, tolerance and so on.

It should be noted disappointed statistics. More than 5 billion people have died in 14,000 wars over the past 500 years. The number of casualties, the scale of the wars, the aggression, the brutality, and the number of countries affected by the fighting are growing every year. Some armed conflicts have been going on for decades, and interstate conflicts are becoming continuously. In addition to open hostilities, the world commits 500 million criminal offenses annually, or 0.08% per capita. The planet is on fire of violence and aggression. The situation is becoming critical due to the development of the weapons of mass destruction industry. Is there a reasonable way out, a way to the peaceful existence of mankind? People on our planet have never been so close to each other. With one click, the phone and Internet resources connect people from different continents, countries and religions. But in the same way the actions of scientists, politicians of a particular country respond to the consequences around the world. Nowadays it is visible. Therefore, we are talking about a broad vision of each problem, the formation of plane-

tary thinking, where quantitative indicators are not important, the constructive actions and responsibility for the consequences of human work come to the fore.

The development of Ukraine as a multicultural democratic state contributes to the consolidation of society in the conditions of the peaceful coexistence of different social strata of the population.

The World Economic Forum in Davos, which brought together more than 2,500 cultural figures, financiers and politicians, discussed the Fourth Industrial Revolution for the first time in 2016. Revolution 4.0 is a concept that means the development and merging of automated production, data exchange and production technologies into a single self-regulatory system, with the least or no human intervention in the production process [1].

In the foreseeable future, information technology is gradually moving to the automation of technological processes, artificial intelligence and robotics, which will inevitably lead to the creation of a huge number of jobs. Some professions will remain only in history, while others will come.

Recently, educational institutions of our country have pursued a course on the individualization of the individual, its comprehensive development. There is currently no shortage of information, there is a problem with its processing and appropriate usage. In today's world, children's encyclopedic knowledge and outstanding skills do not surprise anyone. After all, the conflict between the children's team and intolerance of other opinions has increased. Modern children can tell stories, but they find it difficult to listen to others, most of the time they spend alone or with gadgets. At school they are close, but not together.

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is required from the person of the future qualities that will be useful in the management of works, information systems, coordinated cooperation in a single movement. A person must have critical thinking skills, ability to work in a team, negotiate, compromise, think creatively and make decisions.

Following the results of the World Forum in Davos, a list of basic skills for a successful human career has been identified. These skills include a comprehensive problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, people management, coordination of actions with others emotional intelligence, common opinion and decision-making; customer orientation, interaction, the art of negotiation, cognitive flexibility. [2]

The concept of education development in Ukraine in 2015-2025 defines the issue of educating a tolerant personality as one of the leading tasks of educational institutions. In order to reform the education system of Ukraine, it is necessary to focus efforts on creating a new system of child development. Systems, where the process of education is based on mastering the educational material that forms the foundation of a tolerant person, who is able to understand the other and make decisions.

In accordance with the National Strategy for the Development of Education in Ukraine for the period 2021 (2013), the Concept of National and Patriotic Education of Children and Youth (2015), the Concept of

New Ukrainian School (2016), the Concept for the Development of Civic Education in Ukraine (2018) requirements for creating appropriate conditions for the education of tolerance.

On March 2019, at the International Education Forum on the occasion of the annual Global Teacher Prize to outstanding educators, tolerance was identified as the most important component of modern education, and education is the key to tolerance. After all, only educated people can accept global challenges and bring peace to our planet.

World events (wars, epidemics, quarantine, etc.) as a litmus test show the qualities of the personality of each nation and state. Recently, the situation with COVID - 19 has shown the level of spirituality, kindness and tolerance of people. Of course, the population of different countries united in flash mobs of good, emphasized the insecurity of the elderly, people with special needs, which prompted the manifestation of the best mental qualities of the individual, the introduction of measures for psychological support, the provision of a range of educational programs free of charge, assistance to the elderly. But, at the same time, aggression and intolerance among the vulnerable segments of the population have increased significantly. Dissatisfaction with basic human needs, uncertainty about the future, the general pressure of the media creates a situation of hopelessness, confusion, depression and intolerance. It is impossible to imagine the tolerance of the population of prehistoric tribes, if a person has a need to meet the basic physical needs of life (food, roof, clothes). Abraham Maslow told that before a person can pursue any other goals, he must meet these basic needs.

Man differs from animals in that his actions are not guided by physiological needs, he is able to reason, to make decisions with his heart. It is necessary to cultivate a spiritually rich person, a person who understands the other, is capable of compassion, for whom good deeds and charity are a natural manifestation in any situation. And it's better to start from a preschool.

According to the scientific works of prominent teachers (Sh. Amonashvili, I. Bekh, A. Bogush, T. Kravchenko, V. Kuz, A. Maslow, O. Pometun, V. Sitarov, O. Sukhomlinskaya, etc.) it is necessary to cover as early as possible issues of moral development, to acquaint with the concepts of good and evil, to form a human perception of the situation. According to the age periodization of L. Vygotsky's childhood, the sensitive period of assimilation of norms of moral behavior is preschool age. Five-year-old children are already able to compare and evaluate the situation, the formation of self-esteem, which consists of the reaction of others to their own actions.

Results and Discussion. Despite the significant number of scientific papers, the problem of tolerance formation in children of age from 5 to 7 is insufficiently studied, scientists do not pay attention to the specifics of instilling the principles of tolerance of preschool children.

Among the many problems that arise in studying the system of modern practical teachers and constructive experience abroad is a significant scientific interest is a set of issues related to the disclosure of the structure

of the educational process of 5-7 years-old children and justification of its components, identifying approaches to creating systems of optimal principles, innovative approaches, methods of forming tolerance in the conditions of preschool educational institution and primary school.

The need for special research is exacerbated by the existing contradictions: between the existing socio-pedagogical need for the formation of a tolerant future population of the planet and the lack of attention of scientists to create an effective system of education tolerance of scientific and practical nature.

We can predict that during the educational process of modern children, it is necessary to pay more attention to the culture of communication, the ability to negotiate, hear each other, work in a team. It is necessary to grow a tolerant personality, capable of collective decision-making, a person who is responsible for personal actions before society and himself. Tolerance is a way to life, professional, general and social success of everyone, a guarantee of peaceful existence, development of our society, state and future of the planet.

Our children are taking over the world in an extraordinary age. An era of radical change, ambivalence of values and unification of the world, which in turn contributes to interfaith confrontation, exacerbation of conflicts, including inter-ethnic. Tolerance is the basis of understanding between people of different religious preferences, nations and social strata. In our opinion, tolerance is, first of all, recognition of equality and respect of others, which implies non-violent communication, mercy, renunciation of domination. The world around is diverse and unique, there is no other/ There is one planet, one life, one humanity. Tolerance is unity in diversity. Signs of modern society are general instability (ideological, social, legal and financial), lack of guarantees and responsibilities, due to the low level of moral values. Which, in turn, causes uncertainty in the future and confusion. Sometimes, people of the 21st century behave like our ancestors, who fought for the right to life for themselves and their families with weapons in their hands. Cruelty and social aggression indicate the destruction of value orientations, spiritual crisis, lack of a strong moral and ethical basis for raising children, where the focus is on the person as a value. We see that ensuring a socially secure future, tolerance of human relations is essential to create conditions for the humanization of the educational process, partnership, democratic relations between its participants, respect for everyone regardless of the status and age of teacher and student. Create learning conditions that are based on universal values and provide a natural disclosure of the child's abilities in harmony with the world around him.

Rethinking the content of personal education in the current socio-cultural situation requires legislative changes in new education. Recently, the leading legislative documents defining the guidelines of educational activities at the preschool and school levels, emphasize the formation of child's tolerance, the need to raise a respectful, empathetic, polite, peaceful, tolerant personality.

Education in Ukraine is at the stage of reforming and finding new effective methods of working with children. According to the new educational standards, which are based on the Recommendations of the European Parliament and the Council of Europe on the formation of key competences for lifelong learning (2006), it is not learning, but the acquisition of competencies that comes to the fore, which ensures continuity between preschool and primary education in the context of school reform. [3] One of the priorities of the new school is the formation of children's system of universal values – as socio-political (respect for the law, democracy, patriotism, native language and culture, freedom, care for the environment, solidarity, responsibility) and moral ethical (honesty and dignity, respect for yourself and others). At the heart of the new education is the education of children's responsibility for themselves, for the well-being of our country, the formation of a tolerant attitude towards others. And it is necessary to begin this complex multifaceted process from preschool age.

In modern conditions, the problem of tolerance is a prerequisite for national security, peaceful coexistence of man, society, nation, state and so on. Generals are preparing for the last war. This famous statement of Winston Churchill emphasizes the need for forward thinking, education of tolerance from preschool age. It is necessary to learn to conduct a dialogue, change the frame of reference, find new ways of socialization of the person, her education in the atmosphere of respect for achievements of various cultures. The requirement to renounce the use of force as a means of resolving disputes, the ability to seek and find consensus is the rule of the future life of mankind. Local conflicts in modern conditions are dangerous to grow into global ones. Therefore, the search for strategies of nonviolence is a paradigm of human survival. After all, tolerance is a strategy of the future, the slogan of which should be gratitude to the past, solitary conscious actions of the present and responsibility for the future.

The issue of educating a tolerant personality has usually been a priority for human development. Tolerance as the main value of society was considered by scientists, in particular, A. Asmolov, I. Bekh, E. Golovakha, E. Zelenov, I. Zyazyun, V. Pukhlyak, G. Soldatova, L. Khoruzha. In the historical context, the problem of tolerance was addressed by scientists (P. Bale, I. Vyshensky, F. Voltaire, K. A. Helvetius, I. Gisel, M. Hrushevsky, M. Drahomanov, V. Lypynsky, D. Locke, D. Mill, T. More).

In our time, tolerance is becoming an urgent need for the normal development of society, ensuring the peaceful existence of the world. It is no coincidence that F.A. Hayek connects the civic courage, independence of mind, and in this series tolerance with the formation and manifestation of a free personality [4].

Psychological and pedagogical research shows that the senior preschool age is favorable for the formation of moral guidelines of the child. After all, during this period the individual comprehends and assimilates certain moral values, ideals, beliefs, which are directed to the process of spontaneous or specially organized edu-

cation; moral (or vice versa) stamps of behavior, attitude to oneself, relatives and strangers become habitual (L. Artemova, I. Bekh, L. Bozhovych, L. Vygotsky, L. Galiguzova O. Kononko, V. Mukhina, Y. Prykhdoko, A. Royak, V. Slobodchikov, E. Smirnova, S. Jacobson, etc.). In particular, L. Vygotsky proved that the mental development of a child is connected with his social relations, which are formed in the process of individual or collective activity. In addition, the older preschooler awakens an interest in another child's personality that is not related to his or her specific actions. In his peers, he already sees something more than just an object for play, in comparison with himself, so he is able to understand the other, his feelings, without which manifestations of tolerance are impossible [5]. For a 5, 6-year-old child, interpersonal tolerance presupposes the ability to negotiate without shouting and quarreling, behave politely, listen to the other's opinion to the end, understand his feelings and mood. If it is necessary, give in and wait, share toys, talk calmly, do not disturb the game by noisy invasion. The senior preschooler must be able to show a warning and attention to a friend, politeness and care (thank you for your help, apologize for mistakes, ask permission for certain actions if necessary, etc.). Since tolerance is a moral category, its education is carried out in the context of this area. The process of moral education of preschoolers was studied by O. Kulchytska, attaching great importance not so much to children's knowledge of rules and norms of behavior, which, in fact, does not ensure their observance, but the development of moral feelings and moral habits. So, education can give the desired result. The child's consciousness is combined with persistence and painstaking work on the organization of children's exercise in moral behavior, in the formation of their moral habits. Good behavior of the child only becomes an internal need when it is strongly associated with his moral feelings. The child must experience satisfaction or dissatisfaction about their actions, deeds and intentions. Feelings of duty, shame, self-worth, and sympathy for others are very important here. Of course, interpersonal tolerance presupposes human treatment of people. As V. Kotyrlo notes that in preschool childhood this human attitude takes the form of the ability to see and understand the emotional state of other people, come to the rescue, take into account their interests, setting and achieving their goals, considering the moral categories that saturate the semantic field of tolerance, which opposes various manifestations of intolerance in society. At the first place should be the ability to understand the other and self-control, because it is from these traits depends on the degree of acceptance of a person's other view, thoughts, beliefs, convictions, desires, and so on.

Therefore, from preschool age, children should develop identification, which is based on the willingness to consciously put themselves in the place of another person, which contributes to the understanding of their views, attitudes, motives, desires, etc., decentralization (the ability to move away from one's own position, to perceive the point of view of another person). G. Breslav and V. Davydov studied the issue of emotional decentration, which meant the ability of an individual to perceive and take into account in their behavior the

state, desires and interests of other people [6]. Self-regulation, humanity, tolerance, understanding, flexibility, benevolence, empathy, sensitivity, humanity, self-criticism, listening ability, respect, endurance, will, tact, acceptance, recognition - these are some of the categories on which the development of personal tolerance depends.

Scientific and theoretical analysis of psychological and pedagogical sources (A. Bogush, N. Gavrish, A. Goncharenko, T. Ponimanskaya, etc.) on the specifics of the formation of tolerance of a children's team showed that the age of five to seven years is a sensitive period for the formation of behavioral standards, moral norms of existence in society, tolerant relationships. It is at this age that the state of development of the prefrontal cortex, which is responsible for such functions as thinking, logical reasoning, self-control, choosing the most rational course of action, allows the child to understand their own actions and the actions of others and integrate into a social group.

A feature of older preschool children is the need for communication. The moral position of preschoolers is fully revealed through the attitude to the communication partner and joint activities. The assessment of the child's own behavior is formed by the total reaction of others to his actions, which transforms the causal relationships into standards of social behavior. Through the child's emotional response to awareness of the results of the act (approval, condemnation, admiration, experience, etc.), comparison with generally accepted norms of behavior, the child forms an idea of "good" and "bad" and develops self-esteem.

Older preschool age is characterized by the dependence of self-opinion on the reaction of an adult. To the remarks of an adult to one child, her environment responds with the question: "Am I good? Did I do well?" The opinion, the assessment of an adult in preschool age is a compass, by which the child compares his own way and the expediency of his own actions. The results of observation of older preschoolers convincingly showed that children seek to communicate primarily with adults; older children; with peers who have special skills and abilities; children who share common interests. Thus, relationships with peers help the child become more confident, understand their significance, identify their own unique, promote conscious self-perception.

The psychological mechanism that helps to perceive oneself and others is the emotional sphere of the child. The initial stage of development of the need for moral behavior of the child is self-esteem, which in preschool age is manifested through their own emotional state, namely self-blame, self-approval, anticipation of the consequences of their actions. Negative feelings and consequences of some actions build a system of forbidden actions, while positive impressions and emotions, stimulate the child to reproduce friendly behavior, sensitivity, care for others, lay the foundation for future tolerant interaction.

An important factor in the preconditions for the formation of tolerance of a preschool child is the desire to imitate. It is the personal example of an adult that forms the system of moral values, norms of behavior of

a child. The research of Giacomo Rizzolatti, an Italian neurologist, reveals the mechanism of the powerful educational power of imitation. In 1992, Rizzolatti made a breakthrough in the field of brain science, namely, he discovered mirror neurons - unique brain cells that are activated when we follow the actions of other people. These cells, like a mirror, automatically reflect someone else's behavior in the head and allow us to feel everything as if we were doing the action ourselves. They help to subconsciously understand the emotions of another person. This is because due to the imprint in the brain, a person begins to feel the same sensations. Mirror neurons provide understanding of other people without the use of verbal interaction.

Another feature of preschool age is the ability to emote manifestations. L. Strelnikov, studying the issues of emotional development of the child in the context of the problems of his moral education, reveals the peculiarities of the development of empathy in preschool children. The research proves that empathy is a kind of chain of empathy, compassion, assistance and is characterized by the unity of emotional and cognitive components, which are differently correlated at certain stages of development of this process. If the deep motives of the child's action are caused by empathic experiences, the child's moral orientation is formed. That is why it is so important to create an environment for children where the norm of relationships are compassion, empathy, acceptance. The positive emotional background of the family and the friendly atmosphere of the preschool contribute to the formation of socially accepted norms of interaction.

A feature of children 5-7 years of age is the development of emotional intelligence of the child, as an important condition for the formation of the child's regulation of personal behavior, the ability to control their emotions and act consciously.

Education of tolerant relations of senior preschoolers is a process of formation under the influence of specially created pedagogical conditions of the child's personality, capable of conscious characteristic manifestations (useless care and sensitivity; benevolent emotional manifestations and empathy; equal and compliant attitude to others; positive self-acceptance and restraint), which is manifested in communication, actions and joint activities.

The content of education, according to I. Zymnoi, is represented by three components: values, personality traits (qualities) and self-regulation (emotional and volitional component) [3, p. 162]. Accordingly, the content of tolerance education covers all three of the above components, because we consider tolerance as a value, personality quality and principle of behavior. Education in the spirit of tolerance is carried out through the assimilation of values, views and norms of behavior inherent in the ideas of tolerance: the formation of respect for human rights, rejection of violence, tolerance and solidarity; fostering an attitude to the diversity of cultures, their interpenetration and interdependence as a value; instilling a sense of pride in one's national culture, which has developed on the basis of Ukraine's national and cultural diversity, and the desire of ethnic communities to preserve and revive their cultures.

In addition to the assimilation of values, the content of the education of tolerance includes purposeful intellectual, moral, emotional development of the individual in the context of national and in the context of European culture and the culture of mankind in general. It should be noted that the content of education is closely related to relationships as a component of the system, because the relationship is the main mechanism of education. I. Zymnia notes that education in the case of emphasis on values, in particular tolerance, is a mechanism for forming attitudes through the establishment of a personally-significant relationship, its understanding as a component of the existing system of relationships in individual experience, experiencing the fact of establishing this relationship "Language and its acceptance," appropriation", in terms of O. Leontiev [3, p. 164]. Given the formation of personal qualities and self-regulation, the mechanism of education is the solution of certain problems to overcome difficulties, remove contradictions. Such tasks can be considered a direct or indirect meeting with another culture, acquaintance or interaction with other subjects on various subjects of tolerance. Modeling such situations, which remove contradictions or reveal problems that require their consideration and solution, is a specially organized process of forming relationships in a tolerant environment. K. Remarchuk [7] believes that in the process of educating a tolerant personality in modern kindergarten, special attention should be paid to cognitive, emotional evaluative and behavioral criteria.

Cognitive criteria is understanding the importance of mutual expression of humane feelings and friendly attitude (their commitment to another person, sympathy, compassion, friendliness, friendship, compassion, expression of joy at the success of a peer, the desire to please him); awareness of the importance of showing respect for other people's thoughts, ideas and values; the idea that everyone is equal in rights (to play, to express their opinions, etc.); confidence that we must respect the opinion, culture, traditions of the human environment.

Emotional and evaluative criteria include willingness to compare their actions with the moral norms of interpersonal interaction and evaluate others in a friendly manner; the desire to assess the human condition and possible consequences, the further development of a situation in which emotion performs an anticipatory function and encourages the performance of moral actions; ability and desire to evaluate their actions and the actions of others in accordance with the norms of behavior in public places, etc. Behavioral criteria is focused on etiquette formulas, their independent use in situations of standardized speech communication (ability to politely greet and say goodbye during a meeting, listen carefully and do not interrupt a friend, make a polite request, express words of gratitude, apology); the need for comfortable speech interaction with the subjects of communication, as well as the ability to maintain a friendly atmosphere of communication; the ability to show an emotionally positive attitude and cognitive interest in the norms of cultural behavior in theater, transport and other public places; willingness

to understand and accept someone else's way of thinking, feeling, ideas, views or beliefs; respond to the emotions of loved ones; willingness to work with people who differ in appearance, beliefs or language; to show interest in other people's views, recognition of other people's right to their own opinion; to be loyal to strangers; voluntariness, freedom of choice and selflessness in the implementation of values towards others; positive focus on partnership in communication and behavior; friendliness in relations with all peers; willingness to interact constructively and respectfully with people of different nationalities; the ability to be guided by the norms of benevolence in assessing various situations and actions of people; respect for representatives of other nationalities, their language, culture, mutual expression of humane feelings in everyday life, etc. [9].

The child enters school with a certain vision of personal behavior, a certain amount of knowledge about the social norms of morality and self-esteem, which consists of supporting the family environment and the reaction of kindergarten staff. The circle of communication of the child usually changes. Thus, we establish the main functions of tolerance in primary school age, based on the specifics of tolerance itself, as well as the psychological and pedagogical dominants of tolerance education in primary school students. Thus, among the functions that tolerance can perform in the life of a junior high school student, we distinguish the functions of resilience, motivation, adaptability, evaluative-predictive and integrative. The function of stability is to form in students of junior classes an adequate attitude to reality, specific life situations, their own behavior and environment. The motivating function of tolerance provides the beginning of gradual awareness of the junior student of his own position, his own I, which precedes the formation of self-identification and autonomy of his personality. This function determines the motivation of the behavior of the younger student, promotes the development of his critical thinking, broadens his horizons.

The adaptive function contributes to the formation of a positive attitude to constructive cooperation with the development of joint problem solving. The evaluation and prognostic function allows the junior student to gradually expand the contacts of communication, promotes the ability to establish contacts on the basis of open dialogue. Students gradually begin to understand that joint activities are not always based on the same ideas, interests and motives. The integrating function is aimed at overcoming internal collisions with external ones, which are present in micro groups and threaten the preservation of the group. This function provides stability in micro groups, classrooms, schools and stimulates the development of interpersonal relationships between students. Tolerant behavior is manifested in a positive attitude towards oneself. This is a sense of self-worth and the ability to respect the dignity of others, regardless of nationality, ethnicity, religion and social affiliation and individual characteristics; ability to self-knowledge and self-development; positive attitude towards others and friendly attitude to-

wards the world. That is why the family sets the example and lays the foundations for a tolerant relationship. Researchers V. Maralov, V. Sitarov, A. Kozlova propose to begin to form tolerance at preschool age through training and development of endurance, in younger students through the formation of elements of tolerance, in adolescence and senior school age through the development of tolerance. In the primary school age (grades 2–4) the orientation of children in their behavior towards adults is replaced by the orientation towards the group of peers. Increasingly important for the development of the child is his communication with peers, where they learn the relationship of friendship, leadership. The homosexual nature of communication prevails. Tolerance is manifested in younger students in the constant observance of humanistic principles, norms and requirements in relations with people, recognition of the needs and interests of another person, his right to a positive will, orientation to the positive in people, ability to moral improvement, constant focus on another person, respect for his dignity, friendliness, trust, compassion, empathy, kindness, timely help, virtue and mercy.

Conclusions. The main components of tolerance education in primary school students in the educational environment include:

- acquisition of knowledge about tolerance, knowledge about the existence of differences in cultures and ways of thinking of other ethnic, national or cultural backgrounds;

- creation of attitudes to a friendly attitude to another person, as well as to the interest in gaining some experience from communicating with representatives of another culture; development of cultural communication skills and conflict resolution skills. Tolerance of junior school children is determined by the attitudes, habits, worldview formed in the personality; subject to purposeful education and self-education.

The study identified the following criteria and indicators for the education of tolerant behavior in primary school children. Criteria for tolerance:

- cognitive (the presence of knowledge of younger students about the essence and content aspects of tolerance; awareness of the importance of tolerant behavior in society);

- behavioral activity (experience of applying knowledge and skills in behavior; manifested in trust, cooperation, ability to dialogue with others). Based on the criteria and indicators, the levels of the formation of tolerant behavior in junior schoolchildren were determined and characterized. To a high level can be attributed such behavior, which is characterized by the ability to voluntarily help those who need help, the desire to please others, the desire to work together. The student rejoices in the success of others, is generous, shows initiative in useful endeavors, actively condemns the negative actions of others. His language is dominated by words and expressions focused on support, approval. He has a favorable position in the team.

At the sufficient level, there are such actions as helping a friend under the influence of the teacher and the team, support the initiative of others, sympathize with the failures of a friend, shares school supplies and

other things, uses words and expressions of a negative nature. Low level is characterized by such behavior when students do not help and support others, even when they can help, have a tendency to greed, ambition, the desire to stand out (hiding and justifying wrongdoing); mock the physical shortcomings of a friend, invent nicknames. Nature has no value for them. Students who are assigned to this level of development of human feelings, as a rule, are characterized by an unfavorable status in the team. In order to prove that the education of tolerance of primary school children is an integral part of child development, an experiment was conducted, the main task of which was to create a system of education of tolerant behavior of primary school children. The relevance and importance of implementing a system of education for tolerance is that it contributes to the education of the main features of tolerant behavior of primary school students. The main purpose of the education system is to form in children the skills of tolerant behavior. As a result of the implementation of the education system, the following results are expected:

- a student who successfully interacts with the team;
- a student who opposes intolerant relationships;
- a socially adapted student.

Analytical work carried out on the basis of research by scientists on the issue of personality, tolerance (G. Asmolova, N. Ivanova, A. Pogodina, G. Soldatova, G. Allport, O. Ovsyannikova, N. Skrypnyk, etc.), allowed us to identify the essence of tolerance in children five to seven years of age as an integrative quality of personality, which is formed on the basis of knowledge of the world, in all its diversity, richness of different ethnic cultures and determines its desire to communicate, establish social contacts with other people (regardless of their age, physical characteristics, gender, ethnicity), based on understanding, respect and willingness to interact and cooperate.

The central factor in the system of education of the younger generation is the process of education of tolerance, which we consider as the relationship of the following factors:

- purpose (determining the direction of education of tolerance, filled with personally meaningful meaning);

- the content of education (information-effective component of the process, for the formation of tolerance as a quality of personality and principles of behavior);

- means of education of tolerance (combination of forms, methods, means of pedagogical interaction);

- environment (ability to tolerance of all participants in the educational process, compliance of their personal moral values with the principles of tolerance education)

The interaction and functioning of these components are possible under the conditions of upbringing the education, because their absence has a negative impact on the formation of the child's personality. Either family members and teachers raise the child, really aware of the end result, or the children invaluable copy the experience of others (actions, events, random peo-

ple). That is why the issue of creating pedagogical conditions requires more meaningful coverage within this scientific article.

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METHODS OF TEACHING 1ST GRADE STUDENTS TO SOLVE TEXT PROBLEMS

Myrzhikova A.,
Master student of «Pavlodar Pedagogical University named after A. Margulan»,
Higher School of Pedagogy,
Kenenbayeva M.,
Scientific supervisor
Zhaparova B.

1-ШІ СЫНЫП ОҚУШЫЛАРЫН МӘТІНДІ ЕСЕП ШЫҒАРУҒА ҮЙРТУДІҢ ЖОЛДАРЫ

Мыржиқова А.Е.
«Ә. Марғұлан атындағы Павлодар педагогикалық университетінің магистранты, Жоғары педагогика мектебі, Павлодар, 140008, Қазақстан Республикасы
Кененбаева М.А.
Ғылыми жетекші
п.ғ.к., профессор
Жапарова Б.М.
п.ғ.к.

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Abstract

This article deals with the problem of teaching elementary school students various ways of solving text problems. In mathematics lessons, primary school students face various tasks in solving "standard" and "non-standard" tasks of a logical nature that are included in the educational requirements. Therefore, in our pedagogical activity, we tried to form in children a real ability to solve text problems. When compiling and converting calculations, the student develops logical thinking, imagination, a cognitive interest in mathematics is formed, and his creative potential develops. At school, much attention is paid to solving ready-made text problems, but there is practically no work on their compilation and reconstruction. We present this article as a methodological guide that takes into account these issues.

Аңдатпа

Бұл мақалада бастауыш сынып оқушыларының мәтінді есептерді әртүрлі тәсілдермен шығаруға үйрету мәселесі қарастырылған. Математика сабақтарында бастауыш сынып оқушыларының біліміне қойылатын талаптарға енгізілген "стандартты" және логикалық сипаттағы "стандартты емес" есептерді шешуде әр түрлі міндеттерге тап болады. Біз осы мәселелерді ескере отырып, әдістемелік көмек ретінде осы мақаланы ұсынып отырмыз.

Keywords: Primary school, word problems, solution, learning.

Кілтті сөздер: Бастауыш мектеп, мәтінді есеп, шығару, үйрету

Қазіргі кезде мектептердегі білімдер жүйесінен дағдарыс кезеңдерін көруге болады. Мұның мәні – оқыту әдіс-тәсілдерінің жеткіліксіздігі емес немесе мектеп өмірін басқаша ұйымдастыру емес. Бүгінгі күннің негізгі талабы – білімді адамды әлемнің бүтіндей қабылдай алатын, шығармашылық

таныммен тікелей қатынас жасай алатын, жаңаша ойлай алатын шығармашылық адамға айналдыру. **Шығармашылық** – адамның өмір шындығында өзін-өзі тануға ұмтылуы, ізденуі болып табылады. Оқыту процесінде шығармашылық қабілет құрылымы аз қолданылғанымен, ғылыми ізденіс